

EIC User Group Newsletter

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Prepared by

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NEWS

- Improving communication with the EICUG: Over the last few months, there have been several updates to the **EICUG.org** web page. Some useful information to help keep you up to date:
 1. Composition of the various committees and working groups
 2. List of upcoming EIC-related meetings
 3. A repository of useful EICUG documents and newsletters
 4. Agendas and minutes of the weekly Steering Committee meetings
- The **election of a new at-large Steering Committee member** will be initiated in the very near future. The candidates are **Haiyan Gao (Duke University)** and **Barbara Jacak (Lawrence Berkeley National Lab & University of California, Berkeley)**.
- We continue to make additional information available and welcome suggestions on ways to improve communication. Please send suggestions, questions, or input on any topic to John Arrington and Marco Radici.
- Work towards the **EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Studies** is beginning. The purpose is to advance the state of documented physics studies and detector concepts in preparation for the EIC, as well as to provide a basis for further development of concepts for experimental equipment best suited for science needs, including complementarity of two detectors. EIC activities at DOE seem to be proceeding fast, thus the plan is to finalize these studies in approximately 1 year by putting together a Yellow-Report-like document which constitutes input towards future Technical Design Reports (TDR). The Steering Committee has identified conveners for each of the working groups:

1. Physics WG

- Adrian Dumitru (Baruch College, New York, NY, USA)
Email: Adrian.dumitru@baruch.cuny.edu
- Olga Evdokimov (Univ. Illinois at Chicago, Chicago, IL, USA)
Email: evdolga@uic.edu
- Andreas Metz (Temple Univ, Philadelphia, PA, USA)
Email: metza@temple.edu
- Carlos Munoz Cam (IPN-Orsay, Orsay, France)
Email: munoz@ipno.in2p3.fr

2. Detector WG:

- Ken Barish (Univ. California at Riverside, Riverside, CA, USA)
Email: kenneth.barish@ucr.edu
- Tanja Horn (Catholic Univ. of America, Washington, D.C., USA)
Email: hornt@cua.edu
- Peter Jones (Univ. Birmingham, Birmingham, UK)
Email: p.g.jones@bham.ac.uk
- Silva Dalla Torre (Univ. and INFN – Trieste, Trieste, Italy)
Email: silvia.dallatorre@ts.infn.it

- Each WG will be structured in several sub-groups, with 2-3 conveners per sub-group. The **kick-off meeting** will be held at **MIT on December 12-13, 2019**. As an organizational meeting, it is restricted in the number of participants but several sessions will be open to remote connections via Bluejeans. More information will be distributed in due time. Further details can be found at <https://www.jlab.org/indico/event/348/> which is also mirrored in the EICUG web page: <http://eicug.org/>.
- As announced in the previous Newsletter, the Steering Committee has planned four “**Yellow Report Workshops**” to take place in 2020. The dates and locations are:
 - 1st Workshop: 19-21 March 2020, Temple Univ., Philadelphia (USA)
 - 2nd Workshop: 22-24 May 2020, Univ. and INFN-Pavia (Italy)
 - 3rd Workshop: 17-19 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C. (USA)
 - 4th Workshop: 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The EIC User Group (**EICUG**) is **growing!** Currently, it stands at 973 members, from 196 institutions in 31 countries. We welcome the 6 institutions that have joined the EICUG in October and November:
 - Pennsylvania State University Berks (USA)
 - Davidson College (USA)
 - Institute for Nonperturbative Physics at Nanjing University (China)
 - Pusan National University (South Korea)
 - Bhabha Atomic Research Center (India)
 - King Saud University (Saudi Arabia)
 - Tel Aviv University (Israel)
 - Imam Abdulrahman bin Faisal University (Saudi Arabia)

NEWS from the PHYSICS & DETECTOR WORKING GROUPS

The working group conveners have started regular meetings.

Detector WG: November 11, 18, and 25

Physics WG: November 20, 27

A summary from the first Detector Working Group meeting is here:

http://www.vsl.cua.edu/cua_phy/index.php/General_Meeting_Summary_11/11/19

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .
- The proceedings deadline for the INT EIC workshop, “Probing Nucleons and Nuclei in High Energy Collisions” is December 31.

<http://www.int.washington.edu/PROGRAMS/18-3/>

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

<http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes links to some presentations)

- [EIC ad-hoc meeting on detector and physics simulations](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 10 July 2019
- [EIC User Group meeting 2019](#), Paris (France), 22-26 July 2019
- [27th International Nuclear Physics Conference \(INPC 2019\)](#), Glasgow (Scotland), 28 July - 2 August 2019
- [29th Conference on Lepton and Photon Interactions \(LP2019\)](#), Toronto (Canada), 5-10 August 2019
- [Hadron 2019](#), Guilin (China), 16-21 August 2019
- [8th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 19\)](#), Kolymbari (Greece), 21-30 August 2019
- [The 11th Circum-Pan-Pacific Symposium on High Energy Spin Physics](#), Miyazaki (Japan), 27-30 August 2019
- [POETIC 2019](#), Berkeley (CA - USA), 16-20 September 2019
- [Light Cone 2019](#), Palaiseau (France), 16-20 September 2019
- [EIC Software meeting and GEANT4 Technical Forum](#), JLab Newport News (VA - USA), 24 September 2019
- [13th European Research Conference on Electromagnetic Interactions with Nucleons and Nuclei](#), Paphos (Cyprus), 27 October - 2 November 2019
- [CHEP 2019](#), Adelaide (Australia), 3-8 November 2019
- [Quark Matter 2019](#), Wuhan (China), 4-8 November 2019
- [EIC Streaming Readout workshop](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 13-15 November 2019
- [LPC Workshop on Physics Connections the LHC and EIC](#), FermiLab (IL - USA), 13-15 November 2019
- [Forward Physics and QCD at LHC](#), Guanajuato (Mexico), 18-23 November 2019
- [MCEGs for future ep and eA facilities](#), Vienna (Austria), 20-22 November 2019
- [Resummation, Evolution, Factorization \(REF 2019\)](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 November 2019

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

(in addition to the Yellow Report Workshops listed above)

Upcoming meetings list: <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming>

Open EICUG talk list: <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open>

Hadronic Physics Conferences: <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html>

- [CPAD Instrumentation Frontier Workshop](#), Madison (WI - USA), 8-10 December 2019
- [International workshop on QCD with EIC \(QEIC\)](#), Bombay (India), 4-7 January 2020
- [EIC Detector R&D Committee Meeting](#), Upton (NY - USA), 30-31 January 2020
- [2020 Santa Fe Jets and Heavy Flavor Workshop](#), Santa Fe (NM - USA), 3-5 February 2020
- [Winter Workshop on Nuclear Dynamics](#), Puerto Vallarta (Mexico), 1-7 March 2020
- [KEK Workshop on Femtotechnologies by quantum computers 2020](#), Tsukuba (Japan), 7 March 2020
- [DIS 2020](#), Brooklyn (NY - USA), 23-27 March 2020
- [Rencontres de Moriond, QCD and high-energy interactions](#), La Thuile (Italy), 28 March - 4 April 2020
- [QCD Evolution 2020](#), Los Angeles (CA - USA), 27 April - 1 May 2020
- [Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020
- [Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 1-6 June 2020
- [40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 30 July - 5 August 2020
- EIC Users Group Meeting 2020, Miami (FL - USA), 3-7 August 2020
- [Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020
- [22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#), Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020
- [24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25 September 2020
- [Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020
- [Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021
- Quarks and Nucleon Physics QNP 2021, Bonn (Germany), 20-24 September 2021